

Emergence of Technology in Learning- Online Communication Classroom through News Paper Activities

Dr. Sk.Rehena¹, Assistant Professor of English, PVP Siddhartha institute Of Technology, Kanuru, Vijayawada,
Dr. N.Vineela², Trained Graduate Teacher In English,A.P.Model School & College, Reddigudem,
R.V.Nagalakshmi³, S.A.English, Z.P.H.S Eturu, Krishna District, Andhra Pradesh,

Abstract: The rapid advancement of global technology has revolutionized the way the world was functioning to switch from the traditional mode to digital. The major accelerator to choose Digital Methodology in teaching is the Covid-19 pandemic that stroke without a caution. The progress of any Nation to a great extent depends on the Research and Development. The explosion of information is due to the researches in different areas. The technological development is also due to Research. In nutshell the Research is the backbone of any country progress and development. Thus, research is conducted in all disciplines. But it is observed that the society gets maximum benefit from researches conducted in different areas of Science, Medicine and Technology. The findings of researches in Social Sciences are not as useful as those of Science, Medicine and Technology.

Keywords: Digital Methodology, research, development, covid- 19 and information.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the advent of new technologies being infused in school curricula, educators and school leaders are beginning to rethink all facets of data in the classroom. New, innovative methods of data collection are continually being developed, which offer new options for ongoing formative, culminating summative and alternative assessments. Yet what precisely do nouveau “research-based instructional strategies entail? Although challenges in curriculum design may arise due to advanced technology integration, schools are nonetheless embracing the future. Here are five emerging trends for 21st-century classrooms.

Literacy, technological literacy, and 21st century skills, ICT Literacy reflects the need for students to develop learning skills that enable them to think critically, analyses information, communicate, collaborate, and problem- solving, and the essential role technology plays in realizing the learning skills in today’s knowledge-based society. The following six fields are critical to student’s achievements in the workplace.

•**Communicate Effectively:** Students need to possess a range of skills to convey themselves not only through paper and pencil but also audio, video, animation and design software.

•**Analyze and Interpret Data:** Students must be able to analyze and interpret the accumulation of data.

• **Understand Computational Modeling:** Students should possess an understanding of the power limitations and underlying assumptions of various data

•**Representation systems,** such as computational models and simulations, which are increasingly driving a wide – range of disciplines.

•**Manage and prioritize Tasks:** Students must be able to manage the multi-tasking, selection, and prioritize Tasks: Students must be able to, manage the multi- tasking, selection, and Prioritizing across technology applications that allow them to move gracefully along teams, assignments and communities of practice.

•**Engage in a problem solving:** Students must have an understanding of how to apply what they know and can do to the new situations.

•**Ensure security and safety:** Students must know and use strategies to acknowledge, identify, and negotiate 21 st – century risks.

The four key principles which help teachers to implement technology are:

1.**Separate the role of the teacher:** It is important to understand the respective roles played by the teacher and the technology in the learning process.

2.**Teach in a principled way:** Whenever a new technology emerges (such as, say, podcasting), it is important to go beyond the ‘wow’ factor and think about the pedagogical Clear

3.**Use the technology to complement and enhance what the teacher does do with it**

THE ENGLISH TEACHER

To strive in the tycoon of digital transformation, the English language teacher honed capabilities to embrace technology and worked on numerous tools of technology to facilitate the learners on the digital landscape. The ELT practice modernized the learning process of the students with the adoption of ICT.

ADAPTING TO STUDENT NEEDS

Through mails, which were created by the students (a group mail ID to each class) themselves? As I am working/ teaching for undergraduate Pharmacy students and M.B.A post graduate students, they obviously have a Desktop or a Laptop or an Android mobile phone to attend their classes. Apart from the syllabus, I give inputs for competitive exams which really benefit the students. Things came on to the track, but regarding technical issues depend on the power transmission and Internet. The students were suggested to opt for the required internet pack and also to download the apps of digital newspapers on their respective gadgets, so

In a classroom of 60 students, it is virtually impossible for a teacher to find the right approach for everyone. The idea of using digital tools as a methodology by the teacher facilitates the learning needs of each individual student can be taken into consideration. In this methodology the LSRW integrated language learning process, the English teacher can open up many an avenue for personalized learning which surely bears fruit in their future performance.

The digital language learning platform allows learners to work at their own pace, repeating topics and emphasizing things they have trouble with, engaging themselves with the tasks they are best at, and also which are appealing to their interests. This feeling must be captured by the teacher to encourage the students to take on their target language learning.

A REDEFINED ROLE FOR TEACHERS

Digital Methodology redefined the role of teachers and imparting of education. Instead of being the sage on the stage, teachers become the guide on the side, meaning that technology covers up the teachers' mundane tasks while they become more like advisers to learners. The teacher has to coordinate the learning process and mentor students digitally in a more tech-savvy and ambient learning environment to enhance the students' learning process. Teacher guidance and creativity, allied with the digital tools are a powerful means to encourage students' development in their journey of language learning.

Online teaching poses an unusual set of challenges for teachers and students as well. To make the classes effective practically, communication and collaboration on either side is obviously needed to

experience a happy learning environment. Adaptability is important on the part of both the teacher and the students. Technical issues pose a threat to human work and also the output and above all self- motivation on the part of the student is really important. This drives the student to learn wherever they are and also to manage time along with all these challenges of online learning is also an another advantage. It is to be noted that, after quite a few days, students were able to adapt to the online classes and started submitting their assignments that they can work out on comprehensions and reading the editorials to enhance their vocabulary.

DIGITAL NEWSPAPER

The Hindu e Paper and Times of India or any other paper for that matter, which is a digital replica of the daily newspaper are suggested to students. Obviously, students are prone to more user-friendly navigation to search instantly to save stories and share them with friends on social media. They made it easy to access across multiple devices and choice of formats in the form of text, image or PDF, which creates a reading experience that is pleasant and convenient mode. As they were using an Android phone or Tablet or a Laptop, were suggested to download the News App along with the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary. www.vocabulary.com has been suggested to students to enhance their vocabulary.

The following activities were suggested to the students and personally have coupled with the learning outcomes of the same.

EDITORIAL READING AND WRITING

It reveals how the Pandemic changed the way of life like learning from home for students and working from home for teachers. I only asked about how people helped others in terms of charity of various types like distributing food especially was the cause of concern. The charity activities taken up by Tollywood and Bollywood actors all over triggered the students to a mode like participative learning as they volunteered to share such stories and their opinions of the same.

The students read about the migrant laborers, people who did not have proper shelter, food and how they suffered from lack of basic amenities. After all such reading and sharing in the form of discussions, it is really amazing that they developed a sense of human interest. They started empathizing with the people who lacked such basic things and felt that they were really fortunate enough to be in the comfort of their homes. The students of Pharmacy definitely need such thinking which obviously reflects in their profession. M.B.A students perceived all these activities in the mode of team work, social responsibility and how to

tackle societal challenges with a collaborative effort. I suggested them to collect humorous comic strips from the Internet and also from the News papers in regional language also. After a good collection and discussion they came to learn of how they can express in a subtle and humorous way in their collaborations like Debates and pair work.

DIGITAL DICTIONARY

Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary to enhance their vocabulary and usage of idioms and phrases. I introduced in a class about Shakespearean use of English, which we owe even today. I shared an IMAGE on idioms and phrases used by William Shakespeare in his plays and suggested them to use the ones in the IMAGE in their own words. After that they were given an assignment as to collect as many as such expressions by browsing the Internet and also asked to collect information on the contextual usage by the characters in the play. At the time of their sharing of information, they wished to use such expressions in their conversations in future. The activity made them involve in a learning kind of experience and in a way enjoyed to opt for action research in the online classroom.

Communicative learners are more likely to employ communicative language learning approach which intensely focuses on enhancing students' autonomy and control over the language learning process. The teacher also approaches the analytical learners the way they wish to be approached, and that is by giving them certain handouts to read in an offline class. But in an online class the ELT teacher is on a more of a marathon by suggesting some digital materials in an online communication classroom. The teacher has to go on an extra mile in making the students understand the nature of their own mistakes and giving them opportunities to express their point of view whether in Debates or in Group Discussions or any other activity which involves the learning of their target language.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, as teachers we are enablers and drivers of learning whose value increases from the learning success of the student/learner, not from the number of rehearsed sentences or repeated words but in the contextual usage of the target language, whether in an online or an offline classroom.

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How to cite this article?

Dr. Sk.Rehena¹ Dr. N.Vineela² R.V.Nagalakshmi³, "Emergence of Technology in Learning- Online Communication Classroom through News Paper Activities", International Journal of Trends in English Language and Literature (IJTELL) 2(4), PP: 53-55, 2021, DOI: 10.22247/ijtell/2021/209695.